

A Production Planning Solution for Industrial IoT-enabled Manufacturing

Daniel Erzse*

* Asociatia CoderDojo Oradea
Oradea, Romania
daniel.erzse@coderdojo.ro

Arnold Nilgesz†

† Octavic PTS
Oradea, Romania
arnold.nilgesz@octavic.ro

Paul Harfas†

† Octavic PTS
Oradea, Romania
paul.harfas@octavic.ro

Abstract—A modern completely automated production requires knowledge on availability of not only machines but also working shifts and stocks. This global knowledge on the resources has been possible through Industry 4.0 that enables gathering data from all resources. Such knowledge enables a careful production management and planning that increases productivity and flexibility, and improves product quality. While unexpected events such as machine breakdowns may intrupt the predefined production plans, the new functionalities enabled by Industry 4.0 can predict them.

In this paper, we target Industrial IoT-enabled manufacturing environments where data collection enables modeling of workshop, stocks, production demand and working shifts. We are interested in determining precise production planning for all machines with the goal of optimizing the production and delivery. We have proposed a Constraint Programming (CP)-based solution to this problem, and developed accurate system model, which, together with a metaheuristic search employed in the CP solver can drive the search quickly towards good quality solutions. We have evaluated the proposed strategy on several test cases including realistic test cases and also validate the resulted plans in real-world manufacturing.

Index Terms—Optimization, Production Planning, IIoT

I. INTRODUCTION

The new industrial revolution (Industry 4.0) will bring increased productivity and flexibility, mass customization, reduced time-to-market, improved product quality, innovations and new business models. With Industry 4.0, Operational Technology (OT) and Information Technology (IT) which are currently separated in a hierarchical pyramid (Purdue Reference Model [1]) and use different computation and communication technologies, converge. OT consists of cyber-physical systems that monitor and control physical processes that manage, e.g., automated manufacturing, critical infrastructures, smart buildings and smart cities. OT uses proprietary solutions, imposing severe restrictions on the information flow.

On the contrary, IT uses different computation and communication technologies that are optimized for dealing with increased scalability and performance, storing and manipulating data [2]. IT brings flexibility and capabilities for faster development and improvement with Cloud Computing, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Big Data.

As information technology (IT) and operational technology (OT) come together, manufacturing undergoes an unprecedented shift as long-standing barriers between the digital

and physical domains of production erode. This combination facilitates a smooth flow of information across all production levels by integrating OT's management of physical equipment and processes with IT's data processing and analytics capabilities. It makes real-time data collecting and analysis accessible to anything from CEO dashboards to shop floor sensors. Because of this interconnection, quick and informed automated decision-making procedures have become possible, greatly increasing operational efficiency. The ability to quickly obtain actionable insights helps in anticipating and resolving such problems before they become escalated and need costly downtime. Additionally, this connectivity provides the flexibility needed for rapidly changing production schedules.

When Industry 4.0 technologies are incorporated into manufacturing processes, a number of advantages arise which together completely change the dynamics of production. The most important of these is the never-before-seen data visibility across the production process. Manufacturers can get real-time insights into all aspects of production, from raw material condition to equipment performance data, using IoT devices.

Better operational efficiency becomes possible using this comprehensive perspective, especially by using predictive maintenance techniques. By using data analysis, predictive algorithms can foresee equipment problems before they happen, significantly minimizing unscheduled downtime and extending the life of equipment. In addition, Zhong et al. (2017) clarify how IoT may be strategically used for predictive maintenance and how IMS (intelligent manufacturing systems) can have a revolutionary effect on operational efficiency, highlighting the importance of these technologies in contemporary industrial environments [3].

Furthermore, the development of customized and adaptable manufacturing lines becomes possible by the flexibility provided by IoT and data analytics. Manufacturers can swiftly switch from mass manufacturing to mass customization with minor disruption by quickly adapting to changing customer requirements or market trends.

The importance of artificial intelligence and data analytics cannot be overstated. Collecting and analyzing the huge amounts of data generated by Internet of Things devices requires knowledge in each of these domains. Tao et al. (2018)'s exploration of the idea of "digital twins" comes up as a crucial novelty in this area [4]. By using big data

analytics to improve product design, production, and service, digital twins—virtual copies of actual systems—allow for a better synchronization between the digital and physical worlds. AI assists decision-makers optimize production workflows, improve product quality, and reduce waste by turning raw data into actionable insight. This supports more intelligent, creative, and efficient production decisions.

Production planning has entered a revolutionary phase as a result of the combination of operational technology (OT) and information technology (IT), shifting from old, static procedures to dynamic, agile processes. The Smart Factory idea, which shows how IT-OT integration has been crucial in improving the adaptability and efficacy of industrial operations, is an expression of this shift. Production plans may be quickly adjusted to reflect operational data in real time, straight from the factory floor to digital planning systems, thanks to the seamless integration of technology. This kind of dynamic planning ensures efficient use of equipment and supplies, thus decreasing waste and optimizing the distribution of resources. Production planning has advanced significantly, paving the way for more adaptable and productive manufacturing processes [5].

Furthermore, studying the broader implications of Industry 4.0 and smart manufacturing shows how the integration of IT and OT technologies improves production planning, increasing its flexibility and effectiveness. Therefore, combining the use of IT and OT technologies gives companies a competitive edge in the quick-paced industrial sector in addition to streamlining manufacturing processes [6].

Industry 4.0 has drastically changed the production planning environment, yet current methodologies often fall short of achieving its full potential. Although fundamental, traditional production planning techniques generally cannot include real-time data and predictive analytics—features that are essential to Industry 4.0 technology. Their effectiveness is limited in the rapidly shifting production settings of today as a result of this gap. These traditional methods fail to accurately forecast future disruptions or dynamically react to changes in the absence of real-time data from IoT devices. Predictive analytics also lacks potential for proactive changes that might save costs, time, and maximize resource utilization in planning procedures.

New approaches to production planning are urgently required, solutions that utilize the advantage of IoT data and use it to increase operational efficiency and planning precision. Such methods would be a big step forward, ensuring that production planning is predictive as well as responsive, and more in line with Industry 4.0's aims.

By leveraging the potential of Industry 4.0 technology, our research proposes an innovative approach to production planning that directly solves the drawbacks of current techniques. Our primary contribution is in the strategic integration of real-time Internet of Things data into the production planning process, which significantly improves the flexibility and productivity of manufacturing processes. We enhance production schedules adopting Constraint Programming (CP) methods, which account for the complex relationship of variables and

constraints encountered in contemporary industrial contexts, in a way that is not achievable with conventional techniques. Because of the dynamic nature of this optimization, production plans may be continuously modified in accordance with changes in production capacity or demand that take place in real time.

Our approach significantly improves production systems' responsiveness, helping them to foresee changes in the manufacturing environment as well as respond to them. By this study, we reduce the information gap between Industry 4.0's theoretical promise and real-world implementation, offering businesses a clear road map to enhance their production efficiency and flexibility in an ever-changing marketplace.

Going beyond this basic outline, the article offers an innovative method for optimizing production timelines by integrating real-time data from IoT devices with complex Constraint Programming (CP) methods. The adaptability and operational effectiveness of industrial systems are greatly increased by this original method. The article's major body is dedicated to a comprehensive analysis of our technique, including how it was used and how its implications have been evaluated. This provides a clear picture of our research process.

II. MOTIVATION

One of the best examples of a real-world factory that has completely accepted and begun to use Industry 4.0 technologies is Siemens Electronic Works in Amberg, Germany. This production facility is well known for its complex use of digitalization, automation, and integrated manufacturing processes. Programmable logic controllers, or PLCs, are produced in the Amberg plant. PLCs are an essential component of automated manufacturing systems all around the world. [7]

Every PLC on the assembly line is controlled by a digital product memory, which ensures that each phase of the production process is carried out precisely. This system allows for real-time tracking and quality control, with over 75% of the production process being automated.

The complexity of managing an advanced manufacturing process comes from the requirement of efficiently combine data from multiple sources, including machinery, supply networks, and quality control systems, to optimize production planning and execution. The Siemens facility addresses these issues by utilizing smart data analytics, adaptive manufacturing techniques, and predictive maintenance. This enables the facility to anticipate maintenance needs and minimize downtime, as well as respond to fluctuations in production demand or supply chain disruptions with minimal manual intervention.

The Siemens Electronic Works in Amberg proved the concrete benefits of digital transformation in manufacturing through the use of Industry 4.0 technologies, resulting in exceptionally impressive levels of productivity and quality. The factory has reported a defect rate of less than 11 parts per million. This example shows how integrating digital technologies with conventional production processes may greatly improve operating efficiency, flexibility, and product quality.

Production scheduling is naturally challenging in a facility as sophisticated and networked as Siemens Electronic Works because so many variables need to be taken into account at once. The necessity of maintaining strict quality and efficiency standards while remaining flexible in reaction to shifting consumer demands and possible supply chain disruptions adds to this complexity. The incorporation of Industry 4.0 technology enables more informed and flexible decision-making processes, which are essential for handling this degree of complexity.

Considering the manufacturing of Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) as an example, rigorous and accurate job coordination along the production line is required for the highest possible process planning. In order avoid bottlenecks, raw materials need to first be determined and prepared, ensuring that the correct parts are available when needed. After that, each PLC component goes through a number of steps of assembly, testing, and quality control, with specific tasks being delegated to machines that are equipped with cutting-edge sensors and control systems.

In order to achieve the most effective planning for PLC production, these jobs have to be managed to maximize efficiency and include flexibility to deal with real-time data inputs. For example, in order to maintain overall productivity, the production plan must be right away changed to redirect duties to other machines or temporarily prioritize alternate components if a machine performing a vital task in the assembly line needs unexpected maintenance. Similar to this, in the event of a sudden spike in demand for a specific kind of PLC, the production schedule must be quickly adjusted to increase output without compromising the quality of the final product. This may involve reallocating resources or extending work shifts.

Predictive analytics is also used in optimal planning to foresee demand and recognize possible supply chain disruptions before they happen. The Siemens factory can proactively change its production plans by evaluating data patterns, which helps reduce waste and inefficiency while maintaining alignment with market demands.

III. SYSTEM MODELS

In this section we present the system model which consists of (1) a workshop modeled described in Section III-A, (2) a stocks model described in Section III-B, and (3) a application model described in Section III-C. The overall structure and interactions between these components are illustrated in Figure 1. Additionally, the notation used throughout this discussion is summarized in Table I

A. Workshop model

We model the workshop as a set of machines $\mathcal{V}$. Each machine ν_i performs a specific operation on materials, and is characterized by the tuple $\langle l, \Delta \rangle$, that are the duration of operation in seconds and the set of working shifts of the machine. Each working shift $\delta_j \in \nu_i.\Delta$ is a tuple $\langle \alpha, \beta \rangle$ which represents the start and end of each shift in seconds.

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF THE NOTATION

Symbol	Notation
$\mathcal{V}$	Set of machines
$\nu_i \in \mathcal{V}$	Machine
$\nu_i.l$	Operation length
$\nu_i.\Delta$	Set of working shifts
$\delta_j \in \Delta$	Working shift
$\delta_j.\alpha$	Start of the working shift
$\delta_j.\beta$	End of the working shift
$\mathbf{D}$	Machine switching time function
Φ	Set of materials
$\phi_i \in \Phi$	Material
$(A)(t)$	Material availability function
$\gamma_i \in \Gamma$	Application
$\gamma_i.d$	Deadline
$\gamma_i.\mathcal{M}$	Application RARM function
$\gamma_i.r$	Set of operations
$\gamma_i.r_j$	Candidate machines for operations
γ_i^j	Task
$\gamma_i^j.\phi$	Task offset
$\gamma_i^j.l$	Task length

We define the function $\mathbf{D} : \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$, which takes the machines ν_i and ν_j as input and returns the switching time from the machine ν_i to the machine ν_j in seconds.

B. Stocks model

We model the stocks with a set of materials Θ that are required for the production. Each material $\theta \in \Theta$ is associated with an availability function $\mathcal{A}(t)$ that returns the available material in kg at the time t . Note that the amount of the available material is given without considering the consumed amount, i.e. we assume that no materials are consumed.

C. Application model

We model the products as a set of applications Γ , where each application γ_i is associated with the tuple $\langle d, \mathbf{U}, r \rangle$ that are the deadline for the product delivery in seconds, the required amount of raw material (RARM) function, and the production procedure, respectively.

The RARM function $\mathbf{U} : \Theta \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ takes the material θ from the stocks model and returns the required amount of it in kilograms.

The production procedure r is the set of operations needed to manufacture the product, that is modeled as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) where the nodes are operations. Each DAG starts with a source operation and ends with a sink operation. Each operation starts only when all its input are arrived, and terminates when it is completed. The total number of operations in the production procedure r is denoted with $|r|$, and the i^{th} operation is captured with r_i which returns the set $\mathcal{V}_i \subseteq \mathcal{V}$ that are the listed candidate machines for performing the operation.

We define a task for each operation $1 \leq j \leq |r|$ of the application γ_i , and denote it with γ_i^j . A task γ_i^j is associated with the tuple $\langle \phi, l \rangle$ denoting the start time of the frame (offset ϕ) and its duration (length l).

Fig. 1. The IoT-Enabled Manufacturing Cycle Workflow: Highlighting the Interaction of Application, Workshop, and Stock Models

IV. PROBLEM DEFINITION

We formulate the production planning problem as follows: Given (1) a workshop model $\mathcal{V}$, (2) a stocks model Θ , and (3) an application model Γ ; we are interested in determining the production plan such that (a) all the applications in the system are manufacturable (their deadlines are satisfied) and (b) the all applications are delivered in the shortest time, as the delivery metric defined in Sect. V-C, is minimized.

Synthesizing the production plan is equivalent to determining (i) the tasks' offsets $\gamma_i^j \cdot \phi$, and (ii) the tasks' length $f_i^j \cdot l$.

V. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The scheduling and planning problems as decision problems have been proved to be NP-complete in the strong sense [8]. To this end, we propose an optimization strategy called Stocks-aware Production Planning Strategy (SaPPS), based on a Constraint Programming (CP) formulation.

CP is a declarative programming paradigm that has been widely used to solve a variety of optimization problems such as scheduling, routing, and resource allocations. With CP, a problem is modeled through a set of variables and a set of constraints. Each variable has a finite set of values, called domain, that can be assigned to it (see Section V-A). Constraints restrict the variables' domains by bounding them to a range of values and defining relations between the domains of different variables (see Section V-B).

SaPPS visits solutions that satisfy the constraints defined in Section V-B and evaluates them using the objective function defined in Section V-C to check if the solution is an *improving* solution, i.e., better than the best solutions found so far.

Stock Model

- Material availability in stocks model crucially affects the production schedule.
- System checks for required materials' availability in adequate quantities before scheduling product production.

Application Model

- Application model sends operation sequence to workshop model post-production scheduling.
- Workshop model allocates machines and schedules operations, factoring in: machine availability, operational capabilities, working shifts, operation duration, machine switching times, planning operations within machine working shifts.

Workshop Model

- Workshop model updates stocks model on material consumption during manufacturing.
- Stocks model adjusts inventory levels based on updates.
- Ensures accurate material availability representation for future planning.

A. CP model

The mapping function $\mathcal{M}$ which captures the mapping of operations to the machines is defined as a decision variable. The domain and the co-domain of the function is defined in Eq. (1) where the function domain is the set of all operations in the operation procedure of applications and the function co-domain is the set of all candidate machines for performing the operation.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{M} : X &\longrightarrow Y : \\ X = \{r_i | r_i \in \gamma_j \cdot r, \gamma_j \in \Gamma\} & \quad Y = \{\mathcal{V}_i | \mathcal{V}_i \subseteq \mathcal{V}\} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

We also define two sets of decision variables for the CP model, which are associated with the tasks' offsets and the tasks' lengths respectively. Each decision variable is associated with a domain from which the CP solver decides the variable's value. The decision variables and their domain are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \forall \gamma_i \in \Gamma, \forall j \in [1, \dots, |\gamma_i \cdot r|], \\ \nu_x = \mathbf{M}(\gamma_i \cdot r_j) : \\ \gamma_i^j \cdot l = \nu_x \cdot l \\ 0 \leq \gamma_i^j \cdot \phi \leq \gamma_i \cdot d \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

B. Constraints

We define five constraints that regulate the manufacturing and relate the domain of the CP variables. CP only finds the feasible solutions, i.e., those where all the constraints are met.

The **Station Overlap Constraint** imposes the restriction on the solution which avoids sharing a machine's resources for

more than one operation at any time. The constraint is defined in Eq. (3).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \gamma_i, \gamma_j \in \Gamma, i \neq j, \\
& \forall k \in [1, \dots, |\gamma_i.r|], \forall m \in [1, \dots, |\gamma_j.r|], \\
& \nu_x = \mathbf{M}(\gamma_i.r_k) = \mathbf{M}(\gamma_j.r_m) : \\
& ((\gamma_i^k.\phi \geq \gamma_j^m.\phi + \gamma_j^m.l) \vee \\
& (\gamma_j^m.\phi \geq \gamma_i^k.\phi + \gamma_i^k.l))
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

We define the **Station Working Shifts Constraint** in Eq. (4) to avoid planning an operation out of the working shifts of machines.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \exists \delta_k | \delta_k \in \nu_x.\Delta, \nu_x = \mathbf{M}(\gamma_i.r_j), j \in [1, \dots, |\gamma_i.r|], \gamma_i \in \Gamma : \\
& ((\gamma_i^j.\phi \geq \nu_x.\delta_k.\alpha) \wedge \\
& (\gamma_i^j.\phi + \gamma_i^j.l \leq \nu_x.\delta_k.\beta))
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The **Application Deadline Constraint** defined in Eq. (5) imposes the restriction that an application is manufactured within its deadline.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \gamma_i \in \Gamma : \\
& \gamma_i^1.\phi + \gamma_i.d \geq \gamma_i^{|\gamma_i.r|}.\phi + \gamma_i^{|\gamma_i.r|}.l.
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The **Production Procedure Constraint** enforces the ordered task operations. We define the constraint in Eq. (6).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \gamma_i \in \Gamma, \forall j \in [1, \dots, |\gamma_i.r|], \\
& \nu_x = \mathbf{M}(\gamma_i.r_j), \nu_y = \mathbf{M}(\gamma_i.r_{j+1}) : \\
& \gamma_i^{j+1}.\phi \geq \gamma_i^j.\phi + \gamma_i^j.l + \mathbf{D}(\nu_x, \nu_y).
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The **Material Availability Constraint**, define in Eq. (7) imposes the restriction on the planning to avoid performing any operations when the required material is not available.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \theta_i \in \Theta, \forall \gamma_j \in \Gamma, \forall \gamma_k \in \Gamma, \gamma_k^1.\phi \leq \gamma_j^1.\phi : \\
& \theta_i.\mathcal{A}(\gamma_j^1.\phi) \geq \sum \gamma_k.\mathbf{U}(\theta_i).
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

C. Objectives

The **Shortest Delivery**, as defined in Eq. (8) is the latest time of all operations for the applications.

Reza: Introduce a function that can distinguish between missing a deadline and maximum laxity!!!!

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall \theta_i \in \Theta, \forall \gamma_j \in \Gamma, \forall \gamma_k \in \Gamma, \gamma_k^1.\phi \leq \gamma_j^1.\phi : \\
& \Omega = \mathbf{Max}\{\gamma_i^{|\gamma_i.r|}.\phi + \gamma_i^{|\gamma_i.r|}.l | \gamma_i \in \Gamma\}.
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Foreach Pending task objective:

$$(task - > end) - (task - > deadline) \tag{9}$$

$$G = \frac{task - > end \times 100}{task - > deadline} - 1 \tag{10}$$

$$Score = G + G \times (G > 0) \tag{11}$$

VI. EVALUATION

A. Methodology and Computational Framework

Computing Environment. We ran experiments on a common computing platform to evaluate our production planning system directly. Although the hardware specifications are not provided here, they were chosen to simulate a conventional industrial data processing job environment. This ensures that the results are repeatable and applicable in a standard industrial setting.

Software Tools. Our computational approach is based on the use of OR-Tools, a powerful collection of tools created by Google specifically for optimization tasks. The advanced algorithms included in the version of OR-Tools used for this study enable it to handle the complex logistics, routing, and scheduling issues that are frequently encountered in production planning. Because of its integrated heuristics, the toolset is especially suitable to the limitations and specifications encountered by IoT-enabled industrial systems. These heuristics are especially effective at handling challenging decision spaces. We used the most recent stable version of OR-Tools, set up to maximize the interaction between our CP model and the solver architecture.

Optimization Tools: Google OR-Tools. Google's OR-Tools is an advanced, portable software package designed to solve combinatorial optimization problems that are common in a variety of industries and businesses. Numerous solutions for linear programming (LP), mixed-integer programming (MIP), and constraint programming (CP) are available in this extensive toolset. The ability of OR-Tools' strong solvers to handle and resolve complex, large-scale optimization problems has made it a crucial tool for operational research as well as a range of real-world uses, including supply chain management, logistics, manufacturing, and telecommunications. The platform is recognized for its versatility, efficiency, and the support it has garnered in the academic and industrial communities, evidenced by extensive documentation and numerous case studies that demonstrate its successful application worldwide. [9]

Language Used for Programming The requirement for computational performance lead us to select C++ as the programming language for developing the production planning models. It is frequently acknowledged that C++ is a reliable language for managing complex algorithmic structures and that it can handle large amounts of data fast. Our CP models, which need a lot of processing power to replicate and enhance industrial production processes, depend on this efficiency in order to operate. Our solution is based on the combination of OR-Tools and C++, which allows us to handle the specifications of production planning in the context of Industry 4.0.

B. Comparative Analysis of Production Planning Approaches

In our study, we contrast a number of widely recognized techniques to a detailed evaluation of a Constraint Programming (CP)-based production planning solution in the context of Industrial IoT (IIoT)-enabled manufacturing. Among these

traditional approaches are the First-Come-First-Served (FCFS) technique, which processes activities in an ordered manner without prioritizing, and Priority Scheduling, which schedules jobs according to pre-established levels of importance. Furthermore, the adaptation of heuristic algorithms like Simulated Annealing (SA) and Genetic Algorithms (GAs) to specific production situations was taken into consideration. Even if they are useful, these traditional approaches often fall short of addressing the variety and volatility present in contemporary production environments.

On the contrary, the CP-based solution offers a comprehensive alternative that can effectively handle the complex dependencies and limitations seen in IoT-enabled setups. A distinctive characteristic of this technology is its dynamic scheduling, which enables adjustments to be made in real time in reaction to unexpected changes in the production environment. It is also very good at maximizing the use of available resources, cutting down on idle time, and increasing throughput in general. The model can provide a degree of planning comprehensiveness that is not possible with traditional techniques due to its ability to navigate difficult limitations associated with machinery, operation sequences, shift timings, and material needs. In addition, its scalability guarantees that it can be used to different manufacturing sizes, establishing the CP-based method as a better choice for sectors looking for more flexibility and optimization in their production processes.

The objective of the review is to examine, both statistically and subjectively, how well the CP-based solution performs in comparison to conventional planning techniques, with a particular emphasis on scalability, computing efficiency, and the overall quality of the solution.

A selection of synthetic test cases have been carefully developed in order to accurately evaluate the efficiency and relevance of the proposed Constraint Programming (CP) technique for production planning in the context of Industrial Internet of Things enabled manufacturing. These test cases covers a wide variety of hypothetical manufacturing situations, from basic, linear production sequences to complexly interconnected, complex procedures that have multiple dependencies and constraints.

The aim of constructing these synthetic situations was to imitate a wide range of operating situations that are commonly seen in the manufacturing industry. Through these test scenarios, key variables have been altered, such as the number of machines in use, the level of work complexity, the diversity of shift patterns, the constraints on material availability, and the degree of urgency for completing order deadlines. The goal of this systematic approach to scenarios development was to examine the operational effectiveness, scalability, and resilience of the CP model under a range of controlled scenarios.

With an emphasis on tracking key performance indicators (KPIs) including the scalability of the model, computational efficiency, and the optimality of the produced production schedules, the test cases were implemented using Google's OR-Tools with the CP framework. The previously mentioned

indicators were chosen to measure the ability of the solution to generate workable production schedules that effectively utilize the resources available, comply with defined timelines, and sustain efficiency in the face of increasingly complicated problems.

In our instance, the following factors were particularly taken into consideration in order to properly evaluate the effectiveness of the production planning system based on constraint programming (CP) in the context of manufacturing facilitated by the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT):

- **Workshift Configurations:** To evaluate the CP model's flexibility in conventional and extended work schedules, a variety of single-shift systems and complex three-shift configurations were used in the scenarios.
- **Deadline Stringency:** The model's capacity to handle production planning issues under a variety of time constraints is demonstrated by the urgency of the production deadlines, which varied from one to three months.
- **Material Availability Constraints:** To verify the model's ability to change production plans in response to shifting resource inputs, test cases were built to account for a range of material availability scenarios, from abundant to constrained.
- **Task Complexity:** Different manufacturing jobs were presented with varying levels of complexity, ranging from simple processes requiring little processing to complicated activities with multiple phases and interdependencies.

Finding out how well the CP model builds production plans that not only maximize the use of resources and fulfill delivery dates, but also show resilience to swings in operational constraints, was the primary goal of the test cases. The assessment was centered on critical performance metrics, including equipment utilization rates, average time per manufacturing order, and schedulability.

The substantial versatility and efficiency of the CP solution is demonstrated by preliminary evaluations of the results obtained from these artificial test scenarios. The methodology proved to be highly effective in meeting deadlines, allocating resources optimally, and being flexible in the face of changing operating circumstances. These results prove the solution's significant potential for broad acceptance in a variety of industrial contexts and emphasize its critical role in achieving Industry 4.0 objectives. In particular, it highlights how the model may greatly increase responsiveness and operational efficiency in IIoT-enhanced industrial environments, which is in line with the strategic goals of smart factory projects.

The effectiveness and feasibility of the Constraint Programming (CP) solution in Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) enabled industrial contexts have been demonstrated by evaluating it in sixteen synthetic and one reality test cases. Three key metrics—schedulability, average production order (PO) time, and equipment utilization rates—were examined in order to evaluate the solution's potential to keep to schedules, maximize operating timings, and make effective use of the resources at hand across a range of manufacturing situations.

The CP model is remarkably good at scheduling production within deadlines; it was able to attain 100% schedulability in most circumstances, especially in those with modified quantities or production orders as shown in Figures 2, 3, and 4

Fig. 2. Schedulability Rates Across Test Cases by Time Interval: A Comparative Visualization of CP Model Performance

Fig. 3. Variations in Schedulability Rates Across Test Cases: A Time Interval Analysis Depicted Through Line Charts

Nonetheless, issues have been identified in situations with strict deadlines or constrained workshifts, as schedulability percentages decreased and equipment utilization rates increased, suggesting increased resource requirements to meet pressing production schedules. Cases with a one-week deadline in particular showed notable performance variability, with schedulability falling as low as 17.24% and equipment utilization rising as high as 80.22%. These findings indicate areas in which the CP model’s capabilities might be further enhanced. On the other side, half-quantity scenarios consistently demonstrated shorter PO times and lower rates of equipment utilization, demonstrating the model’s ability to effectively manage smaller production volumes.

Fig. 4. Comparison of Average Production Order (PO) Time by Time Interval Across Test Cases

This comprehensive evaluation highlights the CP solution’s adaptability and resilience in production planning optimization while also pointing out important areas that still require improvement, especially in managing tight deadlines and allocating resources optimally in high-pressure situations. These discoveries not only validate the CP approach’s capacity to transform production procedures in accordance with Industry 4.0 goals, but they also open the door for CP methodology developments in the future, enabling it to fully capitalize on its advantages in complex and dynamic manufacturing environments.

VII. RELATED WORK

The field of production planning has witnessed notable improvements in operational efficiency and flexibility due to the investigation of many techniques, especially with the emergence of Industrial IoT (IIoT)-enabled industrial settings. This section compares and contrasts the Constraint Programming (CP) approach described in this work with a number of well-known production planning techniques.

Despite their simplicity and ease of use, traditional scheduling techniques like priority scheduling and first-come, first-served (FCFS) frequently fail in dynamic manufacturing environments where task complexity and variability call for more adaptable and responsive planning mechanisms. These techniques are generally ineffective in IIoT situations since they do not take real-time data into consideration.

Heuristic algorithms, such as Simulated Annealing (SA) and Genetic Algorithms (GAs), constitute a major advance because they provide flexible answers to challenging scheduling issues. These algorithms are quite good at searching across large solution spaces for almost-optimal solutions. However, particularly in large-scale industrial applications, their dependence on probabilistic decision-making and repetitive search can result in significant processing overhead.

A mathematically rigorous method for production planning is offered by linear programming (LP) and mixed-integer

linear programming (MILP), which optimize a linear goal function under linear constraints. These approaches struggle with the nonlinearities and discrete decision-making present in many real-world industrial processes, even while they can produce exact solutions for issues that are precisely represented in linear terms.

The study's main emphasis, constraint programming (CP), proves itself to be an extremely efficient method for handling the complex issues associated with IIoT-enabled manufacturing. Production planning can be made more flexible and more adjustable with CP by utilizing real-time data and immediately incorporating a wide range of operational limitations. In contrast to conventional and heuristic approaches, CP performs very well in situations where there are complex limitations and a requirement for flexibility in real time. It offers optimal scheduling solutions that improve operational efficiency and flexibility.

The comparative study illustrates the distinctive advantages of the CP strategy in the context of contemporary production settings. It is a better option for IIoT-enabled industrial settings because of its capacity to manage intricate, dynamic restrictions and include real-time data. In these contexts, conventional, heuristic, and even certain mathematical programming approaches might not adequately capture the nuances of the production scene. As a result, CP offers a pathway to more intelligent, effective, and responsive manufacturing systems while simultaneously addressing the present shortcomings of traditional production planning approaches and aligning with Industry 4.0's strategic objectives.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we explored the revolutionary potential of implementing CP (constraint programming) in industrial contexts enabled by the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). With this integration, production planning methodologies will no longer be used in the same way, and manufacturing processes will become more dynamic, efficient, and adaptive. We intended to address the inherent constraints of traditional planning approaches by utilizing real-time data and advanced CP techniques, therefore aligning with Industry 4.0's ambitious goals.

A new era of manufacturing has begun with the introduction of Industry 4.0, marked by unprecedented levels of data visibility, operational flexibility, and efficiency. The harmonious integration of information technology (IT) and operational technology (OT), which enables real-time decision-making and predictive analytics, is at the core of this transformation. By putting out a CP-based production planning system that uses IIoT data to enhance manufacturing operations, our research adds to this changing field. Our extensive review, which included both artificial and real-world test cases, showed how resilient and flexible the system was in a range of industrial situations. When it came to solving complicated scheduling problems, the CP technique came out because it provided a scalable and effective solution that was difficult for conventional, heuristic, and even certain mathematical programming approaches to match.

In the context of Industrial IoT (IIoT)-enabled manufacturing, an extensive number of research and development opportunities appear as we look ahead, marking the next stage of development for our Constraint Programming (CP) model:

- **Improvement Using Sophisticated Analytical Methods:** The use of artificial intelligence and machine learning is a critical enhancement to the CP model with the goal of strengthening its predictive analytical skills. This improvement will enable a more comprehensive and proactive method of modifying production schedules, responsive to the ever-changing patterns and trends in the industrial environment.
- **Comprehensive Supply Chain Integration:** The CP model is likely to grow in breadth in order to encompass a more comprehensive supply chain perspective. This expanded viewpoint seeks to enhance every stage of the production process, from the acquisition of raw materials to the delivery of completed goods, in order to create a smooth and constant flow of activities.
- **Embracing Novel Manufacturing Technologies:** With the introduction of state-of-the-art manufacturing technologies, particularly additive manufacturing (3D printing), the CP framework will likely go through transformation. This modification presents novel operational restrictions that call for creative solutions in addition to providing new optimization opportunities.

These directions, which are in line with the strategic imperatives of Industry 4.0, highlight our dedication to expanding the CP model's contribution to the manufacturing industry. Our goal is to explore new areas of industrial efficiency, flexibility, and innovation via continuous research and adaptation.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. J. Williams, "The Purdue enterprise reference architecture," *Computers in industry*, vol. 24, no. 2-3, pp. 141-158, 1994.
- [2] R. Rennie and J. Law, *A dictionary of physics*. Oxford University Press, 2019.
- [3] R. Zhong, X. Xu, E. Klotz, and S. Newman, "Intelligent manufacturing in the context of industry 4.0: A review," *Engineering*, vol. 3, pp. 616-630, 10 2017.
- [4] F. Tao, J. Cheng, Q. Qi, M. Zhang, H. Zhang, and F. Sui, "Digital twin-driven product design, manufacturing and service with big data," *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 94, 02 2018.
- [5] D. Lucke, C. Constantinescu, and E. Westkämper, *Smart Factory - A Step towards the Next Generation of Manufacturing*, pp. 115-118. 01 2008.
- [6] K.-D. Thoben, S. Wiesner, and T. Wuest, "Industrie 4.0 and smart manufacturing - a review of research issues and application examples," *International Journal of Automation Technology (IJAT)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 4-16, 2017.
- [7] R. Lal and S. F. Johnson, "The digital factory - siemens: Electronic works amberg." Harvard Business School Case 518-054, November 2017.
- [8] O. Sinnen, *Task scheduling for parallel systems*, vol. 60. John Wiley & Sons, 2007.
- [9] L. Perron and V. Furnon, "Or-tools."